

EFFECTS OF PROCESSING ON THE STATIC AND FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF PEEK/CARBON COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the static and low cycle fatigue behaviour of APC-2 laminates prepared using various molding conditions. Coupons obtained at various molding temperatures and cooling rates are tested under monotonic tensile loading and three-point flexural fatigue conditions. Varying the manufacturing conditions was not seen to have a major effect on the tensile properties of unidirectional laminates. For specimens with multidirectional configurations, molding conditions seemed to mostly affect the yield stress and the strain to failure. The results obtained under fatigue loading, although preliminary, did not show any major dependence on manufacturing parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have fully established themselves as workable engineering materials and are now replacing metals in many applications. With their high specific modulus and strength, improved fatigue properties and their capability of being tailored for a specific application, composites offer a definite advantage compared to more traditional materials.

In the application of advanced polymeric composites, thermoplastic materials such as poly(ether ether ketone) (PEEK), offer a number of significant advantages over the more conventional materials such as epoxy. Furthermore, carbon-fiber reinforced PEEK (CF/PEEK) composites, by virtue of their high service temperature and superior fracture toughness are serious candidates to replace epoxy-based composites in the aerospace industry.

However, since PEEK is a relatively new material, some questions relating to the service life of structures made from this material remain to be addressed. Recent studies [1-5] have shown that the mechanical and physical properties of CF/PEEK are greatly affected by the thermal processing cycle which strongly affects the matrix morphology as well as the fiber/matrix interface properties in the composite.

Results of previous studies [1,2] on the effect of the molding parameters on the interaction between the carbon fiber and the PEEK matrix have shown that all the processing parameters: molding temperature, residence time at melt temperature and cooling rate have an important effect on the interfacial properties of the end product.

Jar et al. [3,4] have also conducted a study on the influence of the various molding conditions on the mechanical behaviour of CF/PEEK. They determined that an increase in cooling rate decreases the delamination resistance only during the initial crack growth and only when the specimens are formed at 400°C.

The effect of the cooling rate on the properties of CF/PEEK has also been reported by Davies et al. [5]. In their work, they examined the influence of the cooling rate on the short and long term properties of the material. They found that, for matrix dominated unidirectional specimens, there was little influence of the cooling rate. For multidirectional laminates under both static and fatigue loading, the slower-cooled panels were shown to have equivalent or superior performance compared to the faster-cooled specimen. They therefore concluded that the internal stresses induced during fast cooling are more detrimental to the performance of the composite than the changes in matrix structure observed at slow cooling rate.

Although considerable attention has been given lately to carbon reinforced thermoplastics, the fatigue behaviour of these materials has only been given a minor fraction of the overall total [6-10]. Several researchers have compared the cyclic behaviour of the thermoplastic composites (CF/PEEK) to those of the thermosetting composites (CF/Epoxy). Some of the results have shown that the former exhibit better fatigue strength but some of the results have also shown the opposite.

A comparative study between thermoset and thermoplastic cross-ply laminates was performed by Henaff-Gardin and Lafarie-Frenot [6]. They concluded that, under monotonic tensile loading, the behaviour of the thermoplastic composite was slightly higher than that of the thermoset composite, but the trend was reversed under tensile fatigue loading.

Curtis et al. [7] studied the zero-tension fatigue of CF/PEEK composites. They studied the effects of various specimen configurations as well as the frequency of loading. They concluded that both the parallel-sided and the width-waisted specimens lead to similar S-N curves. They also found that the use of high frequencies (5 Hz), results in significantly high temperature rise and deterioration of the fatigue performance, especially for $[\pm 45^{\circ}]_{NS}$ specimens. They recommended the use of frequencies below 0.5 Hz when generating fatigue data. In a more recent publication, Curtis et al. [8] studied the zero-tension and the zero-compression fatigue behaviour of $[\pm 45^{\circ}]_{NS}$ laminates at different cooling rates from the melt during consolidation. The tests were run at various temperatures (-55° and 23° for the zero-tension tests and 23° and 120° for the zero-compression tests). They found that for the tensile fatigue tests, the change of temperature did not significantly change the fatigue behaviour. On the other hand, the change of temperature during the compression fatigue tests showed an effect on the cyclic behaviour.

Although several publications evaluated the fatigue properties of thermoplastic composites, very few of the published results were concerned with the flexural fatigue properties of these materials. Buggy and Dillon [9] obtained the S-N relations for unidirectional, crossply and angle ply laminates using three-point-bend flexure test. They compared their results to those of an established carbon/epoxy system. They concluded that the performance in terms of the normalized S-N relations were similar in both cases.

Troignon and Verdu [10] also compared the flexural fatigue behaviour of epoxy and PEEK polymers and composites under three and four points bending fatigue. They concluded that although there was a large difference in the fatigue lives of the two polymers, the matrix seemed to play no role on the fatigue of the composites.

In the present work, the effect of matrix morphology and fiber/matrix interaction resulting from the various bonding conditions on the static and flexural fatigue properties of APC-2 are investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIAL

The material used in this study is the APC-2 prepreg tape consisting of "VICTREX" PEEK reinforced with unidirectional AS-4 graphite fibers with a nominal thickness of 0.125 mm was supplied by ICI.

PROCESSING

Square plates of 150 mm x 150 mm were compression molded in a matched aluminum mold and pressed in a programmable Wabash press permitting reproducible molding cycles. The plaques were molded at 365°C and 400°C; the melt temperature was measured with a thermocouple inserted in the laminates. Heating was done without pressure and when the molding temperature was reached, high pressure was applied. The residence time at the molding temperature was kept constant at 5 minutes. The plaques molded at 400°C were cooled at various rates; this was done by transferring the hot mold to a second press set at different temperatures or by modifying the cooling system of the first press. The cooling rate reported was calculated from the time required to cool the melted sample from 400°C to 100°C, assuming that the PEEK crystallization below 100°C is negligible [11].

THERMAL ANALYSIS

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to evaluate the level of crystallinity in the molded laminates. The tests were performed on a PERKIN-ELMER DSC-7 instrument. Samples of approximately 12 mg were used for the analysis, which was done under nitrogen at a heating rate of 20°C/min.

MECHANICAL TESTING

The laminates prepared had various stacking sequences. For the evaluation of the monotonic properties, laminates of $[0^0]_6$ and $[90^0]_8$ were constructed. For the cyclic loading experiments, laminates with $[(+45^0)_2, (-45^0)_2]_{2s}$ configuration were used. All laminates were prepared under several conditions of molding temperatures and cooling rates.

Straight sided test coupons were used to characterize the static properties of the material under the various molding parameters. Glass/epoxy end-tabs were bonded to the coupons for gripping purposes. The tabs length varied from 25 mm for the off-axis configurations to 50 mm for the $[0^0]_6$ specimens. All tensile specimens had a length of 150mm and a width of 15 mm. Flexural fatigue specimens had dimensions of 80 mm x 25 mm x 2 mm with a span to thickness ratio of 16.

All tests were performed using a computer controlled MTS testing machine Model 810 together with an MTS 458.20 microconsole. For the static tensile tests, the computer recorded the values of the load, axial strain and transversal strain. For the flexural fatigue tests, the computer recorded the maximum and minimum values of the applied load as well as the corresponding deflections under the load application at predetermined cycles during the life of the specimen. Both monotonic and cyclic tests were conducted at room temperature (23°C) at a relative humidity of 50%. Static tests were performed under a constant displacement rate of 0.2 mm/min. Three-point-bending fatigue tests were undertaken in a sinusoidal load-controlled testing mode, with a load ratio of 0.1 and a frequency of 0.5 Hz. Short beam shear tests (ASTM-D2344) were also performed on laminates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DSC ANALYSIS

Table 1 shows the molding conditions and the morphological characterization of the APC-2 laminates. As expected, the level of crystallinity of the PEEK matrix in the molded laminates is dependent on the cooling rate; the crystallinity decreases as the cooling rate increases. Moreover, it can also be observed that the rapidly cooled specimens annealed at 230°C for one hour show crystallinity similar to samples cooled at the intermediate cooling rate.

Analysis of the DSC thermograms shows evidence of secondary crystallization for the slowly cooled specimens. In fact, while at intermediate and fast cooling rates, the melting behavior is characterized by only one melting peak, at the low cooling rate of 0.8°C/min the thermogram is characterized by two peaks; the higher temperature peak being associated to the melting of the dominant or primary lamellae and the lower to the melting of the crystallites between them. Previous work has shown that secondary crystallization occurs for cooling rates lower than 5°C/min [12].

While it has been already shown that the molding temperature affects significantly the crystalline structure of the PEEK matrix in the composite [13], results of Table 1 indicate that this does not seem to affect the level of crystallinity. The same level of crystallinity is observed for laminates molded at 365°C and 400°C. This result is in accordance with literature data [14-18] indicating that, for a thermoplastic matrix, the melting temperature affects the number and the size of the crystalline entities but does not alter the ultimate crystallinity of the composite.

Tabl. 1. Molding conditions and morphological characterization of APC-2 laminates

	Molding Temperature (°C)	Cooling Rate (°C/min)	% Crystallinity
Condition A	400	0.8	39
Condition B	365	19	34
Condition C	400	19	34
Condition D	400	70	30
Condition E	400 + Annealing to 230°C for one hour	76	33

STATIC TESTS

Tensile strengths, failure strains, elastic moduli and Poisson's ratios for the unidirectional layups were considered for the various molding conditions. For the $[0^0]_6$ specimens, the variations observed show a higher failure stress and strain for the specimens prepared under conditions B & C (average cooling rate). The specimens manufactured using condition D (fast cooling) showed the smallest failure strain, while those with slow cooling (condition A) showed the smallest value of failure stress. The variation in the values of the elastic modulus and the Poisson's coefficient are not as important, however the specimens manufactured using condition D (fast cooling) showed the highest values. Although it is well known that varying the manufacturing parameters affects the properties of the matrix and not the fibers, the variations observed are very likely due to a slight orientation angle in the fibers during the cutting of the specimens. Fig.1 shows the variation of the failure stress and the elastic modulus for the various processing conditions; each point on the curve is an average of 4 to 7 specimens.

Figure 1. Effect of molding conditions on the tensile properties of [0⁰]₆ APC-2
 (a) Failure stress (b) Failure strain (c) Elastic modulus

The variation of the molding parameters for the [90⁰]₈ configuration showed a slight effect on the monotonic properties. The lower values observed for the fast-cooled specimens (condition D) is probably due to the combined effect of reduced matrix crystallinity and residual stress since an annealing treatment (condition E) leads to a significant increase of the failure stress (Fig.2). However, it should be noticed that while annealing leads to an increase of the failure stress, this stress never reaches the value of the slow-cooled specimens. Presence of a certain level of porosity in the quenched specimens (introduced when removing the pressure while moving the mold from one press to another during the cooling process) are probably also responsible for this low value especially for the annealed specimens (condition E). Previously reported work [5] found no effect of molding conditions on the static properties of [90⁰] laminates except above the glass transition temperature of the PEEK matrix (145°C).

Figure 2. Effect of molding conditions on the tensile properties of [90⁰]₈ laminates
 (a) Failure stress (b) Elastic modulus

Figure 3 shows the effect of molding conditions on the short beam shear strength of the unidirectional APC-2 composite. While the molding temperature does not seem to affect the short beam shear strength, the cooling rate has a significant effect on that property. An increase of the cooling rate from 0.8°C/min to 70°C/min results in a decrease of the short beam shear strength from 91 MPa to 73 MPa. Two parameters can be affected by the variation of the cooling rate: the crystalline morphology of the material and the residual stress. As pointed out by Chapman et al. [19], most residual stresses are induced in the region of the cooling stage near the glass transition temperature which is about 145°C for the PEEK matrix

In order to study the effect of each contribution, two annealing treatments were performed on the fast-cooled specimens. First, an annealing treatment at 150°C, in the domain of the glass transition temperature of the PEEK matrix, which has as a function to eliminate the residual stresses in the composite. And, a second annealing treatment at 230°C for one hour (condition E) which also permits a relaxation of the residual stresses but in addition leads to an increase of the level of crystallinity in the composite.

Short beam tests performed on these two series of annealed specimens show that while the annealing treatment at 150°C had no effect on the short beam shear strength value, the treatment at 230°C increased the short beam shear strength from 73 MPa to 80 MPa. These results suggest that the interfacial shear strength in this composite is strongly related to the crystalline matrix morphology at the fiber/matrix interface.

Figure 3. Effect of molding conditions on the short beam shear strength of APC-2 composite

Figure 4 shows the load-displacement and load-deflection curves for laminates with $[(+45^0)_2, (-45^0)_2]_s$ configuration under tensile and three-point-bending loading respectively. The results show that although these curves are very similar for the bending case, the variation is much more pronounced for the static tensile tests where, as expected, the yield stress increased with the increase of crystallinity in the laminate. Although the failure loads are not greatly affected by the variation in molding condition, the failure strains are significantly lower for condition A. The brittleness of the slow-cooled specimens can be related to its high level of crystallinity. Similarly, the specimens that endured a fast cooling process then were annealed (condition E) showed lower failure strain than the laminate with similar cooling conditions without annealing (condition D).

Figure 4. Monotonic tensile (a) and bending (b) tests on [(+45°)2,(-45°)2]2s laminates

LOW CYCLE FATIGUE TESTS

Static and fatigue three-point-flexural tests were performed on [(+45°)2,(-45°)2]2s laminates manufactured using the various molding conditions. Flexural stresses were calculated from the classical beam equation according to the formula [9]:

$$\sigma = \frac{3PL}{2bh^2} \tag{1}$$

where:

- σ = flexural stress (MPa)
- P = applied load (N)
- L = distance between supports (mm)
- b = specimen width (mm)
- h = specimen thickness (mm)

The first results from a detailed program investigating the effect of the molding conditions on the flexural fatigue behaviour of laminates with various layup configurations are presented in Fig. 5. The fatigue lives obtained from the present tests fall within the scatter band of those reported by Buggy and Dillon [9] for the same value of the ratio between the maximum applied stress and the flexural strength. Although more tests are necessary to draw definite conclusions, the preliminary results are in agreement with those presented by other researchers in [5,7] where no definite difference in fatigue life is observed for laminates with various cooling rates. These results also agree with those presented by Totignon et al. [10] who showed that the variation in the matrix properties seems to play no role on the fatigue life of the composite.

Figure 5. S-N curve for [(+45°)2,(-45°)2]2s laminates molded under various conditions

CONCLUSION

Static and flexural fatigue behaviour of APC-2 composites prepared using various manufacturing conditions were examined. As expected, the level of crystallinity of the PEEK matrix in the laminate was found to be dependent on the cooling rate. As the cooling rate decreased, the level of crystallinity in the matrix increased significantly and at the very low cooling rate of 0.8°C/min evidence of secondary crystallization could be detected. The monotonic properties of the matrix dominated unidirectional laminates showed lower values for the failure stress for the fast-cooled condition. For the multidirectional laminates, the axial load-displacement curves are dependent on the cooling rate: lower cooling rates resulted in lower values of the failure strain while the highest failure strains were observed for the fast-cooled specimens. The failure stress however were not affected by this variation in the molding parameters. The short beam shear strength also showed a variation with the cooling rate; a higher strength was observed for the slow-cooled specimens. The results from the low cycle fatigue tests, although preliminary, did not show any major dependence on the molding conditions.

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